

The Mislabeled of the Siege on Gaza as a ‘War’ between Israel and Hamas

Christine Schwöbel-Patel and Nahed Samour

Christine Schwöbel-Patel is Professor at Warwick Law School and Director of the Centre for Critical Legal Studies.
Email: christine.schwobel-patel@warwick.ac.uk

Nahed Samour is a Research Associate in the research project "Race-Religion-Constellations" at Radboud University, Nijmegen and Fellow at Center for Security, Race and Rights, Rutgers Law School. samour@post.harvard.edu

The events of October 7th 2023 did not ‘start a war.’ Rather, as Ralph Wilde has argued, the events marked “a new phase in an ongoing illegal use of force” by Israel (Wilde 2023). The new phase began when, far from entering prisoner exchange negotiations or putting Hamas leaders on trial, Israel launched a systematic armed offensive against Palestinians in Gaza (Reuters 2023). Some states, international organizations, and lawyers were at the time quick to speak out in support of Israel’s ‘right to self-defense’ (Financial Times 2023). What was then a moral outrage at the unexpected attacks by Hamas has been continuously framed as a ‘war,’ giving legitimacy to the self-defense argument made by Israel. The offensive by Israel has, some five months later, killed over 31,000 Palestinians (Middle East Monitor 2024).

Under international law, where the terminology of ‘armed conflict’ is used instead of ‘war,’ the current offensive on Gaza cannot – and could not – be justified as falling under a right to self-defense. Article 51 United

Nations Charter (UNC) regulates the right of a nation state to use force in self-defense. It can only be invoked in response to an ‘armed attack,’ understood as the *beginning* of hostilities. It cannot be invoked as part of ongoing hostilities, as is the case here. Otherwise, each party to the conflict would be in an absurd situation of claiming self-defense every time an attack is made. Israel does not have a right to self-defense within occupied Palestinian territory, because *it is the occupying power*. The International Court of Justice (ICJ) advised already twenty years ago that Article 51 UNC has no relevance with respect to Israel as an occupying power (ICJ 2004).

The relevant international legal framework is in this case the law of occupation. The law of occupation, which is a subfield of international humanitarian law, recognizes occupation as a reality of armed conflict, but restricts its use in terms of temporality. At the latest since the 1967 war, Israel forced large parts of formerly Palestinian land under military occupation. In the Gaza Strip,

Israel militarily tightened control of land access since 2007 and enforced a total naval blockade since 2009. Various Security Council resolutions, which are binding under international law, underline the illegality of Israel's *prolonged* occupation.¹ Due to Israel's systematic, widespread, and ongoing legal restrictions on all aspects of Palestinian life, it has been described as an apartheid regime (Human Rights Watch 2021).

And yet, Israeli voices have repeatedly claimed that Gaza is no longer under occupation because Israel gave up its settlement policy in the Gaza Strip in 2005. However, these ignore the control Israel continues to exert over essential services, like water and electricity, and the ongoing blockade. It also ignores UN Security Council Resolution 1860, which confirmed that Gaza is an 'integral part' of the territory occupied since 1967.

A more accurate label, then, is the terminology of a 'siege', the essence of which is complete isolation from reinforcements and logistical supplies (Emanuela-Chiara Gillard 2019). Abandoning the 'war' terminology, which is associated at least historically with a basic level of equality of arms between the parties, more clearly puts Israel in the frame as an illegally occupying power that has been fundamentally discriminating against Palestinians for decades and has now intensified its operations.

There may be costs connected with the unsettling of the 'war' terminology in favor of 'siege' under conditions of an ongoing occupation. One question is: Do the same protections apply for civilians in an occupation as in a 'war'? Notably, the Geneva Conventions, which regulate warfare to prevent excesses

of conflict, provide for the scenario of occupation. Common Art. 2 of the Geneva Conventions extends the scope of protection to cases of partial or total occupation. Common Art. 3 in any event provides for a minimum standard of protection in any armed conflict, including occupation. This includes the prohibition of targeting civilians and care for the wounded and sick. These provisions apply to all the signatory States of the Geneva Conventions of 1949 and their Additional Protocols of 1977, including Israel. Nonstate actors such as private citizens, armed groups, national liberation movements, and international organizations are also bound by these minimum standards, including Hamas. A further question is: Can certain atrocities still be referred to as 'war crimes' in an occupation? Under international criminal law, the crimes committed outside of war qualify as crimes against humanity (Art. 7 Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court). There is no hierarchy in terms of severity or level of accountability between war crimes and crimes against humanity.

Rather than labelling recent events a 'war' – which implies a single event sparking hostilities and a minimum of equality of arms – it is legally, politically, and morally correct to refer to a siege by Israel, the occupying power, on the Gaza Strip. The bottom line, though, is that regardless of a 'war' or a 'siege', the probability of a genocide being committed lays bare the powerlessness of (counter-hegemonic) international legal arguments vis-à-vis the power of settler colonialism. ♦

1 Since 1967, UN Security Resolutions 252, 476, 478, and more recently 2334 have explicitly prohibited Israel's belligerent occupation.

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